

On 1,3,5-Triazines, Part-IV : Synthesis of 3-Aryl-2-Phenylimino-4-Oxo-6-Arylimino-1,3,5-Thiadiazines and 3,5-Diaryl-2-Thio-4-Phenylimino-6-Oxo-Hexahydro-1,3,5-Triazines

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The synthesis of 3,5-diaryl-2-thio-4-phenylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines involving interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride and 1,5-diaryl-2-thiobiurets has been described. These have been formed through an intermediate 3-aryl-2-phenylimino-4-oxo-6-arylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazines. The phenyl isocyanodichloride unexpectedly did not react with S-benzyl derivatives of 2-thiobiurets.

CERTAIN 1,3,5-triazines involving phenyl isocyanodichloride has been synthesised earlier^{1,2}. The present paper describes the synthesis of 3,5-diaryl-2-thio-4-phenylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines.

Interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride and 1,5-diaryl-2-thiobiurets :

When interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride³ (I) and 1,5-diphenyl-2-thiobiuret⁴⁻⁶ (IIa) has been carried out in boiling benzene/chloroform medium, hydrogen chloride was eliminated and a yellow acidic product, m.p. 203° (d) was isolated. The product was soluble in hot alkali. It afforded a picrate, m.p. 148°, when its ethanolic solution was treated with aqueous picric acid. On pyrolysis, odours of phenyl isocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate were perceptible. It was found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The ir spectrum of the product clearly showed the presence of bands due to -NH stretching at 3250, $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1740, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1610 and C-S-C band at 690 cm^{-1} ⁷⁻⁹. On the basis of these facts, it was suspected to be a 1,3,5-thiadiazine, for which structure 3-phenyl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-oxo-1,3,5-thiadiazine (IIIa) has been suggested.

On warming with ethanol IIIa was converted into a new product, m.p. 256°. It was assigned the structure 3,5-diphenyl-2-thio-4-phenylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IVa) on the basis of the following facts.

It was soluble in hot alkali. It did not give a picrate. On pyrolysis, smells of phenyl isocyanate along with phenyl isothiocyanate were quite perceptible. It was found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution.

On refluxing the ethanolic solution of the product with benzyl chloride (1 : 1) followed by basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide, a pale yellow

product, m.p. 214° was isolated. The ir spectrum of this product clearly showed the presence of bands due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1730, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1620, $\delta\text{S}-\text{CH}_2$ wag at 1230 and two more bands at 1550 and 750 cm^{-1} , characteristics of isotriazine ring structure⁷⁻⁹. On the basis of these facts the product with m.p. 214° has been assigned the structure 3,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-2-mercaptobenzyl-6-oxo-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (Va). Attempted synthesis of Va by the interaction of VIIa and I failed.

The alcoholic suspension of the product with m.p. 256° on refluxing with conc. hydrochloric acid afforded a new product, m.p. 248°. It was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. The ir spectrum of the product clearly exhibited the presence of bands due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1735 and 1720, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1625 and two more bands at 1550 and 750 cm^{-1} , which were characteristics of isotriazine ring structure⁷⁻⁹. It was, therefore, assigned the structure 3,5-diphenyl-4,6-dioxo-2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (VIa).

The ir spectrum of the product with m.p. 256° clearly indicated the presence of bands due to -NH stretching at 3240, $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1730, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1620 and two more bands at 1550 and 750 cm^{-1} , characteristics of isotriazine ring structure^{7,8}.

The reaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride was found extendable to other 1,5-diaryl-2-thiobiurets (IIb-IIe) and corresponding 3-aryl-2-phenylimino-4-oxo-6-arylimino-1,3,5-thiadiazines (IIIb-IIIe) have been isolated. All these products were successfully isomerised to 3,5-diaryl-2-thio-4-phenylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines (IVb-IVe) in presence of hot ethanol.

The mechanism of formation of III, IV and hydrochlorides of VII may be represented in Scheme 1.

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TABLE 1—3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-OXO-6-PHENYLIMINO-1,3,5-THIADIAZINES (III) AND 3,5-DIARYL-2-THIO-6-OXO-PHENYLIMINO-HEXAHYDRO-1,3,5-TRIAZINES (IV)

Sl. No.	1,5-Diaryl-2-thiobiuret (II) (g)	1,3,5-Thiadiazine (III)					1,3,5-Triazine* (IV)			
		m.p. °C	g	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)			m.p. °C	g	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)	
				N%	S%	Eq. wt.			N%	S%
a	1,5-Diphenyl- (5.4)	203 (d)	5.8	13.15 (13.71)	7.18 (7.83)	382.6 (408.5)	256	3.1	14.67 (15.05)	8.24 (8.61)
b	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl- (5.7)	172 (d)	4.9	12.81 (13.23)	7.08 (7.57)	397.6 (422.5)	234	2.8	14.23 (14.51)	7.86 (8.29)
c	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-5-phenyl- (5.7)	179 (d)	5.2	13.72 (13.25)	7.94 (7.57)	394.8 (422.5)	243	3.0	14.19 (14.51)	7.83 (8.29)
d	1- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl- 5-phenyl- (6.1)	176 (d)	4.8	13.02 (12.63)	7.45 (7.23)	418.2 (443.0)	248	2.6	13.42 (13.78)	7.36 (7.87)
e	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- 5-phenyl- (6.1)	185 ^a (d)	5.0	13.14 (12.63)	7.73 (7.29)	420.5 (443.0)	252	2.8	13.36 (13.78)	7.46 (7.87)

* Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained in all cases..

Scheme 1

Experimental

Formation of 3-aryl-2-phenylimino-4-oxo-6-aryl-imino-1,3,5-thiadiazines (III) and 3,5-diaryl-2-thio-4-phenylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines (IV) :

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl) are as follows :

To a benzene suspension of 1,5-diphenyl-2-thiobiuret (0.02 mole ; 5.4 g in 50 ml) was added

phenyl isocyanodichloride (>0.02 mole ; 4 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. Evolution of hydrogen chloride was quite perceptible. On concentration and cooling a semi-solid separated out which on trituration several times with petroleum ether (60-80°) afforded a yellow acidic solid, (IIIa), (5.8 g), recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 203° (d). (Found : N, 13.15 ; S, 7.18 ; Eq. wt. 382.6. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4SO.HCl$ requires N, 13.71 ; S, 7.83% ; Eq. wt. 408). On treatment of ethanolic solution with aqueous picric acid, it afforded a picrate, recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148°. (Found : N, 15.84 ; S, 4.91. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4SO.C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N, 16.31 ; S, 5.32%).

The compound (IIIa) (1.5 g) when warmed with ethanol (20 ml), a new solid, (IVa) (0.8 g) recrystallised from ethanol/acetic acid, m.p. 256° was isolated as an isomeric product. (Found : N, 14.67 ; S, 8.24. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4SO$ requires N, 15.05 ; S, 8.61%).

The ethanolic solution of IVa (0.0065 mole ; 2.4 g) mixed with benzoyl chloride (0.0065 mole ; 1 g), on refluxing for 2-3 hr and subsequently rendered basic with dilute ammonium hydroxide yielded a pale yellow solid (Va) (1.1 g) recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 214°. (Found : N, 11.78 ; S, 6.44. $C_{23}H_{22}N_4SO$ requires N, 12.12 ; S, 6.93%).

The alcoholic suspension of IVa (1.5 g) was mixed with conc. hydrochloric acid (15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6-7 hr. It dissolved gradually and reappeared after some time. It was filtered and the separated acidic product (VIIa) (0.6 g) recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 248°. (Found : N, 13.68 ; S, 10.33. $C_{15}H_{11}N_3SO_2$ requires N, 14.14 ; S, 10.77%). The filtrate on concentration gave aniline hydrochloride, m.p. 196°.

Interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride and 1,5-diaryl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (VII) :

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl) are as follows :

To a benzene suspension of 1,5-diphenyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiuret (VIIa) (0.02 mole ; 7.2 g in 40 ml)

was added a benzene solution of phenyl isocyanodichloride (>0.02 mole ; 4 g in 10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. The residue resulting on concentration, was treated with petroleum ether (60-80°) when a gray coloured acidic solid, a hydrochloride of VIIa, (6.9 g) crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 156°, was isolated. (Found : N, 11.03 ; S, 8.48 ; Eq. wt. 369.4. $C_{21}H_{19}N_3SO.HCl$ requires N, 10.57 ; S, 8.05% ; Eq. wt. 397.5).

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References

1. P. P. PATHE and M. G. PARANJPE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20B**, 824.
2. P. P. PATHE, M. W. AMBEKAR, N. M. NIMDEOKAR and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 670.
3. G. M. DYSON and T. HARRINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 191.
4. M. G. PARANJPE, M.Sc. Project, Banaras Hindu University, Banaras, 1961.
5. S. P. DESHMUKH, M.Sc. Project, Nagpur University, Nagpur, 1979.
6. H. P. KAUFMANN and K. LUTHJE, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1961, **293**, 180 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 24725a.
7. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER in "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1967.
8. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY in "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1961.
9. M. AVRAM and G. D. MATRESCHU in "Infrared Spectroscopy; Applications in Organic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.